

Comparing publication profiles of Finnish universities, state research institutes and universities of applied sciences

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In this study we use eight field-normalised indicators to analyse publication profiles of Finnish universities, state research institutes and universities of applied sciences across major fields of science. Data consists of 162,362 publications (years 2019–2021) from the national VIRTIA publication information service. Results indicate that the three research sectors differ considerably in their publication profiles. While universities of applied sciences are more distinct from universities and state research institutes overall, analysis by fields of research shows also variation between all sectors. Field-normalised indicators show that differences with regard to science communication, multilingualism and bibliodiversity, as well as domestic publishing and collaboration are mission driven rather than based on distinct field profiles. Publication data across sectors improves our understanding of heterogeneity of institutional landscape across fields of science. We conclude that assessment and funding criteria need to consider the mission of the institutions and the institutional background of individual researchers.

1. Introduction

Responsible research assessment calls for the recognition of the diverse contributions of institutions and individuals to science and society (CoARA, 2022). The landscape of higher education and research performing institutions is typically heterogeneous not only in terms of fields and disciplines but also in terms of sectors and institutions as well as orientations towards research, education and societal needs (Lepori, 2022; Santos, 2022). Publication databases such as Scopus and Web of Science which have been typically employed in bibliometric analyses cover English-language scientific publishing well particularly in STEM fields but do not provide an adequate picture of publishing across publication types, languages and fields of science (Sivertsen, 2019).

This study aims to understand the heterogeneity of institutional landscape and its effect on knowledge production and communication across major fields of science by comparing publication profiles of three institutional sectors in Finland: universities, state research institutes and universities of applied sciences. We use multidimensional indicators developed for an earlier study to analyse publication profiles in these three sectors (Auranen & Pölönen, 2023). Using multiple indicators brings forward the variety of organisations' publishing profiles including linguistic diversity (Linkov et al., 2021), different audience and collaboration structures (Ylijoki et al., 2011).

Although all three sectors participate in scientific knowledge production their tasks and audiences differ. Traditionally, the main goal of universities has been producing basic research for the academic community as research institutes have focused on producing applied

research for the means of industry and political decision-making (Late & Puuska, 2014). While the universities of applied sciences are teaching-oriented institutions they have focused on producing applied research for professional development and innovation activities (Renfors, 2014). However, the tasks and goals of these three sectors have blurred during the last decades as the role of scientific knowledge has increased in producing innovations and societal impact and publication indicators have been included in their funding instruments. Therefore, it is important to understand and compare their publication profiles using multidimensional indicators as heterogeneity is one of the main critical issues in the assessment of their performance (Bruni et al., 2020).

University sector in Finland comprises 14 universities, universities of applied sciences sector 24 UAS and state research institute sector 12 SRIs. Lists of organisations in each sector are available on Research.fi, a service offered by the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture that collects and shares information on research conducted in Finland (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2024). Missions of each sector are described in Table 1. Our analysis is carried out at the level of sectors, not individual institutions. While institutions within each sector have different profiles (Auranen & Pölönen, 2023; Late, 2014), it is also relevant to investigate differences at the level of sectors because institutions in a given sector have in common a legally defined mission and also incentive structures based on public funding mechanisms. For example, the allocation of public funding to universities in Finland is partly (14% of core-funding) based on research output, while a small share (2%) of UAS funding is based on publications addressed to professional and general audiences. The funding criteria of SRIs differ between ministries.

Table 1: Missions of the different sectors

Universities	Universities of Applied Sciences	State Research Institutes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - promote independent academic research - provide research-based higher education - universities shall promote lifelong learning, interact with the surrounding society and promote the social impact of university research findings and artistic activities (Universities Act, 558/2009)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - provide higher education for professional expert tasks and duties based on the requirements of the world of work - support the professional growth of students. - carry out applied research, development and innovation activities and artistic activities - promote industry, business and regional development and regenerate the industrial structure of the region provide opportunities for continuous learning (Universities of Applied Sciences Act, 932/2014).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - conduct solution-oriented research that supports societal decision-making and business sector - perform a variety of expert and official tasks as well as fee-based and other service activities - maintain significant research infrastructures, datasets and long time series from different sectors of society - provide services horizontally for most administrative branches, the public sector, companies and third sector actors (Research.fi)

2. Methods and data

We created a publication dataset from VIRTAs Publication Information Service, consisting of 162,362 publications from publication years 2019–2021, of which 101,054 are peer-reviewed publications. Data includes publications from 14 universities, nine SRIs, and 23 UAS which validate and report publication data to VIRTAs service. Of all the nine main types of publications used in VIRTAs service our data includes five: peer-reviewed scientific articles, non-refereed scientific articles, scientific books, publications intended for professional communities and publications intended for the general public. The majority, 75 %, of all publication outputs come from the universities, 7 % are from SRI and 17 % from UAS sectors. For publication year 2021 the number of outputs in the dataset is not entirely complete.

We use the following field-normalized indicators for multidimensional analysis of publication output (Auranen & Pölönen, 2023):

1. Science communication: share of not-peer-reviewed publications aimed at professional and general audiences of the total number of publications.
2. Bibliodiversity: share of peer-reviewed book publications (chapters, monographs and edited volumes) and conference articles of the total number of peer-reviewed publications.
3. Multilingualism: share of peer-reviewed publications in languages other than English (Finnish, Swedish and other languages) of the total number of peer-reviewed publications.
4. Domestic publishing: share of peer-reviewed publications in journals and books published in Finland of the total number of peer-reviewed publications.
5. Domestic collaboration: share of peer-reviewed publications with co-authors from more than one Finnish university of the total number of peer-reviewed publications.
6. International collaboration: share of peer-reviewed publications with co-authors affiliated with foreign institutions of the total number of peer-reviewed publications.
7. Research performance: share of peer-reviewed outputs in JUFO levels 2 (“leading”) and 3 (“top”) publication channels of the total number of peer-reviewed publications.
8. Open access: share of peer-reviewed open access publications, including gold, hybrid and green OA of the total number of peer-reviewed publications.

Field-normalization is important because the different dimensions of publication output differ considerably according to the field of science (Auranen & Pölönen, 2023). We have calculated field-normalized indicators for multidimensional analysis of publication output. For each indicator, the sector’s share in each of the 6 major fields of research was divided by the national average for all three sectors, the quotient was multiplied by the number of sector’s outputs in each of the major fields, and their sum was divided by the total number of sectors’ outputs. For each indicator, the national average (here: average among the three sectors) is 1.

The institutions in the three sectors (namely universities, SRI and UAS) have very different disciplinary profiles: SRI have a larger share (84%) and UAS a smaller (34%) share of STEM research output compared to universities (60%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Shares of major fields of science in total output of publications of the university, state research institute and university of applied sciences sectors in Finland in 2019-2021

Figure 2: Shares of main publication types in total output publications of the university, state research institute and university of applied sciences sectors in Finland in 2019-2021 (peer-reviewed articles and scientific books combined)

3. Results

In this section we describe the main results of our analyses for each dimension of university, SRI and UAS sectors' publication output. Figure 2 shows the basic distribution of publication types in each sector. Figure 3 provides an overview of sectors' publication profiles across major fields of research according to eight field-normalized indicators. Figure 4 looks at sectors' publication profiles for each indicator separately according to major fields of science.

The three sectors differ considerably with regard to the target audiences of their publication output: larger share of SRI publications (35%) and a much larger share of UAS output (89%) is addressed to professional and general audiences compared to universities (17%) (Figure 2). Considering the differences in fields and target audiences, it can be expected that the output of universities, SRI and UAS is very unevenly represented in the international databases, such as WoS and Scopus. Even if we look only at the peer-reviewed publications, 66% of the

universities' output is published in journals with JIF (Journal Impact Factor) - for SRI the share is 78% and for UAS 40%.

Figure 3 indicates that universities' and SRIs' publication profiles resemble each other according to several indicators while UAS have different profile compared to universities and SRIs. Particularly in terms of science communication and domestic publishing UAS are more than twice above national average (1). Also worth noticing is that SRIs are clearly more oriented towards science communication than universities. On the other hand, publication profiles of SRIs and UAS converge in regard to some indicators, especially in domestic collaboration.

Figure 3: Multidimensional indicators for publication profiles of the university, state research institute and university of applied sciences sectors in Finland in 2019-2021.

3.1. Science communication

The university, SRI and UAS sectors differ dramatically in terms of target audiences (Figure 3). Universities are focused on producing peer-reviewed scholarly outputs in academic/scholarly channels and have the lowest value across fields on the indicator based on the share of publications intended for professional and general audiences (Figure 4). This is in stark contrast to the UAS sector, in which the indicator has the highest value across all fields of research and especially in Natural sciences, Engineering and Medical and health sciences. Although, the SRI sector also prioritises the peer-reviewed output in the academic fora, the indicator for science communication is clearly above the average. The emphasis on science communication in the SRI sector is visible especially in Natural sciences, Engineering, Agriculture and Social sciences.

3.2. Bibliodiversity

Looking at the peer-reviewed publication output, some differences appear between sectors based on the diversity of publication types and formats (Figure 3). Bibliodiversity indicator shows the highest values for the UAS sector followed by the university and the SRI sector. Figure 4 shows disciplinary differences between the sectors. The indicator confirm the more bibliodiverse orientation of UAS in peer-reviewed publications as they are distinguished by more frequent use of conference and book publications especially in the Natural sciences,

Engineering and Agriculture, possibly to make knowledge more accessible to audiences beyond academia. The SRI sector stands out with the highest indicator value in the Medical and health sciences showing a different profile compared with other disciplines and sectors.

3.3. Multilingualism

There are relatively small differences between the sectors based on the diversity of languages used in peer-reviewed publications (Figure 3). The indicator value presenting the share of output in Finnish, Swedish and languages other than English is lowest in the SRI sector, followed by universities, and the highest in the UAS sector. Figure 4 shows that with regard to multilingualism the sectors differ relatively little from field specific publication patterns. As regards the STEM fields, in Natural sciences and Engineering, all sectors publish practically their entire peer-reviewed output in English, while in Medicine and health sciences both SRI and UAS, and in Agriculture the UAS, show higher degree in multilingualism. Surprisingly the indicator value for the SRI sector in Arts and humanities is very low. This could be due to the small share, and possibly also the type, of Arts and humanities research published in the SRI sector.

3.4. Domestic publishing

The university, SRI and UAS sectors differ considerably with regard to the use of domestic channels in peer-reviewed publications (Figure 3). The lowest indicator value in domestic publishing is observed in universities and followed by the SRI sector, while the highest value is found again in the UAS sector. Figure 4 shows some differences between the disciplines. Especially in the UAS sector Natural sciences and Engineering stand out with high indicator values that differ from other sectors. Also Medical and health sciences in both UAS and SRI sectors show indicator values above the national average in domestic publishing.

3.5. Domestic collaboration

The tendency of having co-authors from other Finnish organisations seems to differentiate SRI and UAS sectors from universities (Figure 3). Field-normalised indicators show that domestic collaboration is more frequent in the SRI and UAS sectors irrespective of the field profiles (Figure 4). SRI and UAS sectors have very similar patterns across fields, except in Agriculture, where the very large share of the UAS sector could be due to the very small amount of research and output in this field.

3.6. International collaboration

International collaboration practices in peer-reviewed publications seem to differentiate universities and the SRI sector from the UAS sector (Figure 3). Field-normalised indicators show that universities and SRI follow the same field-specific co-authorship patterns in peer-reviewed publications, whereas in UAS the role of international collaboration is less pronounced (Figure 4). Surprisingly, Arts & humanities stand up in the SRI sector with atypical high indicator value.

3.7. Research performance

Universities and SRI show practically no differences in terms of the research performance, as measured by the indicator of peer-reviewed outputs in JUFO levels 2 (“leading”) and 3 (“top”) publication channels whereas in UAS the indicator value is much lower (Figure 3). These similarities and differences between the sectors are highly consistent across fields, and the field-normalised indicators only confirm the distinction between the university and SRI sectors and the UAS sector (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Multidimensional indicators for publication profiles of the university, state research institute and university of applied sciences sectors in Finland by major field of science in 2019-2021. Note that the scales differ among the indicator graphs.

3.8. *Open access*

Open access practices in peer-reviewed publications seem to differentiate universities and SRI sectors again somewhat from the UAS sector (Figure 3). Overall, the indicator value for peer-reviewed publications including gold, hybrid and green OA is higher for the SRI and university sectors compared to the UAS sector (notice that this analysis reflects the situation in June 2022 when the dataset was created). When looking at field specific differences (Figure 4) the UAS sector has a lower OA indicator value especially in Natural sciences, Engineering and Social sciences, whereas differences are small in Medicine and health, Agriculture, and Art and humanities. Again, SRI show atypically large OA share for Arts & humanities, possibly due to focus on journal publishing.

4. Discussion and conclusions

This paper investigated and compared publishing profiles in three R&D sectors in Finland. Earlier research has focused mainly on the university sector leaving the gap in knowledge on practices in UAS and SRI sectors. Information about publication practices across sectors is much needed, preferably based on publication data that covers different types of research output and publication languages. Our analysis of publishing profiles using multidimensional indicators and comprehensive publication data shows clear differences between the three sectors. Whereas publication profiles in universities emphasise the traditional academic publishing practices witnessed by various studies (e.g. Auranen & Pölonen, 2023; Puuska, 2014), UAS sector publishing is more focused on science communication and domestic fora. SRI sector falls between these two extremes as they produce highly ranked international peer reviewed publications but also participate actively in science communication and domestic publishing.

Earlier studies have suggested that research markets (i.e. audiences) for university research follow the disciplinary publication practices (Ylijoki et al., 2011). Our analysis shows the impact of research missions and audiences on publishing practices that sometimes go beyond disciplinary traditions. The examples of UAS and SRI show that even in the STEM fields, publication practices in different sectors can be more diverse and inclusive in terms of science communication, as well as publication types, domestic collaboration, and even languages of peer-reviewed publications. This highlights the importance of situating and contextualising institutional assessment and funding criteria according to the mission of the institutions. Also when assessing individuals for positions and funding, it must be considered that their output profiles are shaped by institutional backgrounds.

The university and SRI sectors have rather similar publication profiles overall although the government basic funding model differs significantly between the two sectors in Finland. Performance-based research funding system used for allocating part of the core-funding annually to universities creates relatively strong incentives in this sector to increase scientific publishing in publication channels - journals, conferences and book publishers - identified as leading (JUFO level 2 and 3) by the Finnish field-specific expert panels. This incentive is absent in government basic funding for SRIs, however, their field-normalised research performance is very similar compared to the university sector. Such findings suggest that publication behaviour is influenced by several factors such as official tasks and funding incentives for research organisations, policy steering from national and international governmental bodies, reward systems of scientific careers and research funding, and disciplinary publication practices.

Due to substantial variations in definition and organisation of university, SRI and UAS sectors among research systems across different countries, the study's findings can be difficult to generalise beyond Finland. It's also worth noting that our analysis of publication data may be incomplete, particularly for research institutes. The funding model in this sector doesn't necessarily encourage reporting publication data in the same manner as other sectors. Also, it is likely that part of the outputs by SRI's and UAS's remain invisible in a purely bibliometric approach (Bruni et al., 2020). For example, producing confidential research reports is evident part of the work in state research institutes (Late, 2014). However, the data we examine provides a more comprehensive and realistic view of publishing practices compared to data collected from databases like Web of Science or Scopus.

The big question raised by our analysis is, what can we expect of research in universities for example in terms of science communication or domestic collaboration? Should it be encouraged to develop characteristics of UAS research, and UAS adopt more research oriented practices typical of the university sector? Or should we rather see sectoral differences as effective division of tasks related to knowledge production and dissemination, in which sectors complement each other rather than should converge.

Open science practices

The original base publication metadata was downloaded from <https://wiki.eduuni.fi/display/cscvirtajtp/Vuositasoiset+Excel-tiedostot>, where also older and more recent datasets are openly available for download.

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Author contributions

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Authors have no competing interests.

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